

CHALLENGES IN ACQUIRING THE SOCIOLINGUISTIC AND SOCIOCULTURAL COMPONENTS OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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***Abstract:** In the given article the problems of developing the components of communicative competence in terms of learning and teaching English as a Second Language are described. The opportunities of improving the analytical skills of students are explained.*

***Keywords:** communication, technical universities, Speaking, Writing, Listening, Reading, language proficiency, personal educational strategies.*

It is important to mention that studying a foreign language by students of technical universities, having a good command of English is essential, no matter which sphere the foreign language will be used, regarding government, business, medicine, law, engineering, military affairs, industrial production, marketing, communication and other fields.

Undeniably, English as a Second Language in technical higher education institutions increases students' interest in improving foreign language skills (Speaking, Writing, Listening and Reading) and creates the basis for good language proficiency. In the process of learning a foreign language, students have the opportunity to improve their analytical skills step by step. The pedagogical, psychological and motivational foundations for the development of students' communicative competence through learning English, developing the personal educational strategies and expanding their vocabulary are considered as significant factors.

The methodology of teaching foreign languages includes a system of knowledge about the rules of teaching English process and methods of influencing the process in order to optimize it. The methodology of teaching English not only reveals the principles of teaching of a foreign language, but also provides its rationale. The methodological component of the content of teaching English is the acquisition of a system of speech skills in a foreign language. The methodological component

consists of teaching students rational teaching methods, developing their ability to use a new language in practice for deeper learning and communication, oral and written.

Moreover, it is important to study different pedagogical approaches in learning a foreign language, since pedagogy is important in education, it helps teachers learn best practices in the classroom and apply them correctly, and expands their understanding. Such types of approaches allow teachers to understand how students learn at different levels and tailor their lessons to those needs. As a result, this process improves the quality of teaching and approach to learning.

Certainly, the benefits of studying English as a major include deep thinking, improve memory, increase ability to perform a number of tasks at the same time, sharpen mind, retention of knowledge for a long time, improve decision-making methods, including skills such as improving academic performance in different languages.

It is in the 21st century that another set of opportunities for foreign language learning is that sharpening the minds of language learners through the acquisition of knowledge is emerging as a powerful way to stimulate the progress of linguistic thinking in the study of English and different foreign languages, field terms, sentence structures, grammatical combinations and ways of expressing thoughts are widely used due to their effectiveness.

The importance of learning English as a second foreign language include five main benefits of learning in the followings: expanding the worldview of language learners, developing thinking skills, improving memory, improving communication skills, new and better acquaintance with cultures, increasing attention and creating wide possibilities.

Approaches to foreign language use are explained by the fact that these approaches are descriptive in nature by focusing on specific aspects of the language used in speech, such as sentence structures (grammar) and phonology (sounds), as well as their details, and are rarely found in the fields beyond literature and linguistics.

Methodology in the process of teaching English to Engineering personnel includes general strategy and reasoning strategy and studies the methods used in various fields and the theories or principles behind them to create approaches in accordance with the objectives. The methodology of teaching a foreign language is embodied in a system of practices and processes used by teachers of the language to support and enrich the teaching methods of students through textbooks and manuals.

In the methodological approach, communicative competence describes the ability to acquire knowledge, including, for example, elementary basic skills such as

reading, writing and arithmetic. Without these skills, no foreign language learner will be able to acquire new knowledge, especially in the process of learning foreign languages.

In fact, the methodology of teaching a foreign language is based on the basic principles of pedagogy, the several didactic principles (consciousness, activity, appearance, systematicity, accessibility, sustainability) are interconnected and regularly complement each other.

There are also several key components of a foreign language curriculum, namely phonemic awareness, phonics, vocabulary development, reading fluency, and interpretive reading skill strategies. This is considered to be the main parameter of reliable approaches in the learning process.

Any type of selective components in the pedagogical and methodological educational process refers to technologies for training English teachers and includes the following stages:

1. Diligence in solving professional problems;
2. Problem solving, goal setting and planning;
3. Development, implementation and presentation of solutions to professional problems.

The importance of proficiency in a Second Foreign Language around the world nowadays shows that the ability to speak English develops more in the process of communication, this process makes easier for interlocutors to understand each other.

Another important aspect of the process is that it occupies the main place in the activity of speech and emotional perception as an opportunity to study a foreign language, improve memory and thinking skills. This situation helps bilinguals remember different symbols, methods, sequences, names and different directions. In addition, language learners are more creative, perceptive and able to concentrate for longer. In the process of learning a language in pedagogy, four main components of language are studied, which include phonology, syntax, semantics and pragmatics.

In conclusion, it should be mentioned that the importance of pedagogy in an educational setting is that it focuses on creating and developing language learners' teaching methods, skills and attitudes, an approach that helps students understand topics in a usable manner and transfer the acquired knowledge beyond the classroom.

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